

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 18.01.2026
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.03.2026
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 13 (129),560-569

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.19360529

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Examining the Effects of Flow Experience and Social Support on AI Companionship

Akış Deneyimi ve Sosyal Desteğin, Yapay Zekâ Arkadaşlığına Etkisinin İncelenmesi

ABSTRACT

This research examines the existence and predecessors of “AI companionship” which has emerged with the increasing use of AI applications not only for functional purposes but also for emotional and relational purposes. The main objective of the study is to determine the effect of perceived social support and experienced flow on users’ friendship like conversational behaviours with AI. Data was collected from 301 individuals between November 27 and December 12, 2025, using convenience sampling and online survey methods, and analysed using SPSS software. The analysis of the collected data reveal that AI social support, traditionally derived from humans and signifying stress reduction, relaxation, or a feeling of well-being, and the flow experience, signifying enjoyment and immersion while chatting with AI, are significant variables in AI companionship. It was also found that 22.3% of participants chatted with artificial intelligence at least a few times a month. Furthermore, differences in research variables based on key characteristics were examined. Finally, the research findings were interpreted, and recommendations were developed for researchers.

Keywords: AI companionship, flow experience, social support, chatting with AI.

ÖZET

Bu araştırma, yapay zeka uygulamalarının sadece işlevsel değil, aynı zamanda duygusal ve ilişkisel amaçlarla kullanımının yaygınlaşmasıyla birlikte ortaya çıkan “yapay zeka arkadaşlığı” kavramını incelemektedir. Çalışmanın temel amacı, kullanıcıların yapay zeka ile kurdukları arkadaşlık benzeri sohbet davranışları üzerinde sosyal destek algısının ve deneyimlenen akışın etkisini belirlemektir. Araştırma kapsamında 27 Kasım-12 Aralık 2025 tarihleri arasında kolayda örnekleme ve online anket yöntemiyle 301 kişiden veriler toplanmış ve SPSS programıyla analiz edilmiştir. Toplanan veriler üzerinde gerçekleştirilen analizler sonucunda; geleneksel olarak insanlardan sağlanan stres azaltma, rahatlama veya daha iyi hissetme gibi anlamlara gelen yapay zeka sosyal desteğinin ve yapay zekayla sohbet ederken eğlenme ve dalıp gitme gibi anlamlara gelen akış deneyiminin, yapay zeka arkadaşlığında önemli değişkenler olduğunu ortaya konulmuştur. Ayrıca temel özelliklere göre araştırma değişkenlerindeki farklılıklar incelenmiştir. Son olarak araştırma bulguları yorumlanmış ve öneriler geliştirilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yapay zeka arkadaşlığı, akış deneyimi, sosyal destek, yapay zeka ile sohbet.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally used for tasks such as answering questions, obtaining information, providing feedback, and making reservations, artificial intelligence applications possess emotional and conversational skills, allowing for the establishment of friendship like relationships. For example, people can form close relationships with AI applications such as ChatGPT, XiaoIce, Alexa, Replika, Siri, and Gatebox. With the increasing use of these applications, AI companionship has become a noteworthy research topic today (Chaturvedi et al., 2024). In short, in addition to the functional use of AI supported chatbots, there is also their use for obtaining emotional and relational value. Despite their widespread use, the relationships between users and AI friends have only recently begun to be researched. For example, in Herbener &

Damholdt's (2025) research, it was determined that 14.6% of Danish high school students had established friendship like interactions with chatbots.

In related research; loneliness, a widespread, significant, and growing public health problem that negatively impacts physical and mental health (Zhou & Zhang, 2024; Patel et al., 2025), and its relationship with AI companionship are researched, suggesting that AI could be a solution to reduce it (Yang et al., 2025; Udd & Nobel, 2025; Liu et al., 2024; Merrill et al., 2022). On the other hand, it is possible to examine the factors affecting AI companionship from different perspectives. This research investigates the effect of the flow experience in AI companionship and the social support received from the AI companions on conversations with the AI or AI companionship.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Artificial intelligence companionship

Advancements in generative artificial intelligence algorithms have led to the introduction of artificial intelligence companions that can engage in conversations covering complex emotions and offer emotional support to humans. Artificial intelligence chat applications, also referred to as synthetic interaction partners, can create the perception of empathy through their responses, even though they do not actually experience emotions (De Freitas et al., 2025). People can also view artificial intelligence applications as friends and use them accordingly. Related research shows that the use of artificial intelligence for chatting purposes is particularly associated with loneliness.

For example, in Vandhika & Sahrani's (2025) field study, a positive correlation was found between loneliness and the use of artificial intelligence companion applications. Related research shows that the use of artificial intelligence for chatting purposes is particularly associated with loneliness. For example, in Vandhika & Sahrani's (2025) field study, a positive correlation was found between loneliness and the use of artificial intelligence companion applications. Similarly, in Udd & Nobel's (2025) research, it was understood that loneliness affects the social use of artificial intelligence. Additionally, it was determined that women are more interested in artificial intelligence in a social context. In short, it has been understood that artificial intelligence can serve as a substitute for social connections, particularly for lonely individuals.

In a field study conducted by Lai et al. (2025) with students, a positive relationship was found between depression, loneliness, and the use of AI for chatting purposes. Furthermore, it was understood that depression significantly influenced this behaviour through loneliness. Jämting's (2025) research determined that highly lonely individuals were more comfortable asking AI personal/private (intimate) and emotional questions. It was also found that socially lonely individuals were more accepting of AI than emotionally lonely individuals.

Research on its effects has shown that AI companionship can have both positive and negative impacts. For example, in a field study conducted by Liu et al. (2024) with users of friendship chatbots, it was determined that some users experienced increased social trust, while others experienced a greater risk of isolation. Marriott & Pitardi's (2024) research showed that AI companionship applications increased user well-being and also led to addiction. Specifically, it was understood that loneliness and fear of being judged, along with increased well-being and AI sensitivity, increased addiction.

2.2. Flow Theory

Flow is used to describe a holistic feeling encompassing complete participation in a behaviour (Csikszentmihalyi, 1977) or a positive psychological experience in the form of complete focus on the present moment (Nakamura & Csikszentmihalyi, 2009). The flow experience is explained with analogies such as flowing like water. The flow experience has been researched more in the context of motivation and performance, such as its effects on musicians (O'Neill, 1999), athletes (Stavrou et al., 2015), and learning (dos Santos et al., 2018; Perttula et al., 2017). Flow, which can also be examined in terms of the work environment, is when a person immerses themselves in a process with an intrinsic desire, without needing external incentives. While in a state of flow, a person feels that time is passing faster than normal. Therefore, flow offers a very enjoyable experience, positively affects the person, and can improve their performance (Yeşiltaş & Türk; 2017). Often associated with high performance and considered a state that offers a positive psychological experience to the individual, flow is linked to happiness, satisfaction, self-development, and experiences that a person can describe as their "best moments." Therefore, it refers to

moments when a person is completely focused on their task, unaware of how time passes, and experiences a high level of pleasure (Metin & Düşmezkalender; 2022).

At this point, flow theory is examined in marketing, online shopping (Nusair & Parsa, 2011; Ozkara et al., 2017; Bilgihan et al., 2014), online gaming, leisure time consumption, experiential marketing, and it is seen that this experience, encompassing focus and enjoyment, can positively influence consumers (Yağcı & Çabuk, 2018). Indeed, flow or optimal experiences is useful for businesses aiming to understand and improve customer relationships in online environments, and these experiences can be expected to positively impact consumers (Obadă, 2013; Hoffman & Novak, 1996). However, the implications of flow theory in the context of artificial intelligence applications do not seem to have received sufficient attention. However, it is observed that AI applications can also affect customers' flow experience (Nguyen et al., 2022), and customers can experience flow on AI-powered websites (Pang et al., 2024) or in the use of AI (Arora et al., 2025).

3. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

3.1. The Impact of Social Support on AI Companionship

Artificial intelligence can be perceived not only as a technical tool but also as a social interlocutor (Scherr et al., 2025). Research supports the idea that AI companionship provides users with social support. Indeed, users can form emotional bonds with AI applications and receive social support from them (Ho et al., 2025). For example, in the research of De Freitas et al. (2025), it was determined that consumers use AI friends to reduce loneliness and that it reduces loneliness more than watching YouTube videos. It was also understood that the feeling of being heard, especially in the user, explains the reduction in loneliness. In the research of Zhang et al. (2025), it was found that those with a narrow social network are more likely to use chatbots for friendship, and this is more pronounced in those with insufficient human social support.

In Herbener & Damholdt's (2025) research, it was understood that Danish high school students engaged in socially supportive conversations alongside utilitarian conversations with their AI friends. Additionally, situational factors such as high loneliness, lack of social support, poor mood, need for self-expression, and feelings of isolation were found to be interaction initiators.

In Pataranutaporn et al.'s (2025) research examining Reddit community discussions about relationships with AI, users reported therapeutic benefits of AI friendship, such as reduced loneliness, readily available support, and improved mental health. Some even engaged in behaviours that concretized the relationship, similar to human traditions such as giving wedding rings. In conclusion, AI friendship appears to be a significant sociotechnical issue.

Jämting's (2025) research suggests that extremely lonely individuals may use artificial intelligence more for emotional support, and while this may provide short-term relief, it can also lead to concerns such as emotional dependency. Syed's (2024) research, which involved interviews, quantitative surveys, and case analysis, found that AI technologies can reduce loneliness. Furthermore, most participants reported improved emotional well-being due to AI companionship. Al Mazroui & Alzyoudi's (2024) research with participants over 60 years old showed that ChatGPT use reduced loneliness. Participants also showed interest, formed emotional bonds, and found it emotionally supportive. Sullivan et al.'s (2023) research, which examined publicly available reviews of the Replika chatbot in the app store, revealed that users reported perceived human-likeness, less perceived loneliness, mental health benefits, as well as perceived emotional support and companionship. Based on these findings and explanations, the first hypothesis of the study is put forward for testing:

H₁: Social support from an AI friend positively effects AI companionship.

3.2. The Impact of Flow Experience on AI Companionship

The AI flow experience is expected to influence AI companionship or conversation with AI. Indeed, AI chatbots can offer entertainment and stress-reducing companionship functions (Ho et al., 2025). At this point, perceived enjoyment is emphasized as one of the most important factors in technology adoption, especially in studies dealing with user-centered applications based on interaction with technology. Similar findings are encountered in the context of artificial intelligence. For example, in Ding & Najaf's (2024) research, it was determined that the perceived enjoyment variable played a moderating role in the effect of trust in AI chatbot adoption. This finding shows that chatbot designers and businesses should design interaction processes as engaging and satisfying as possible so that users can benefit from technology to the maximum extent. In Wang et al.'s (2025) research, it was determined that the perceived enjoyment users

derive from interacting with new technologies positively affects their intention to use AI-assisted design tools. Kim et al. (2025) showed in their research that ChatGPT's ease of use and design features had positive effects on both perceived value and perceived enjoyment levels of users. Furthermore, it was found that these positively influenced the intention to continue using it. In Arora et al.'s (2025) research, it was observed that the flow experience in using ChatGPT for travel planning positively influenced the intention to act accordingly. These studies suggest that the idea that the flow experience in using AI for chat purposes can positively influence this behaviour is worth testing.

H₂: AI chat flow experience positively effects AI companionship.

4. METHOD

This research, conducted using a convenience sampling method, is a descriptive field study. In this context, 308 participants from different socioeconomic statuses were reached through an online survey with obtaining their voluntary consent. Seven outliers were removed, and 301 valid participant data points were analyzed. Design of the questionnaire, prepared to measure the research variables, utilized existing research in the literature. Accordingly, for the three items designed to measure the frequency of AI companionship or conversation with AI for social purposes, adaptations were made from the research of Herbener & Damholdt (2025) and Udd & Nobel (2025). For the six items designed to determine the social support received from AI friends, adaptations were made from the research of Sarason et al. (1987). The response options for these two scales are: "1. Never, 2. Rarely (a few times a year/few months), 3. Sometimes (a few times a month), 4. Frequently (a few times a week), 5. Always (every day or a few times a day)." The four items designed to measure the flow experience while chatting with artificial intelligence were adapted from the research of Wu et al. (2013). The responses consisted of the following options: "1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Undecided, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly agree."

The 301 participants in the study were students (35.9%; 108 people), public sector employees (32.6%; 98 people), private sector employees (18.3%; 55 people), unemployed (10.3%; 31 people), and entrepreneurs (3%; 9 people). In terms of age, participants were 18-28 (52.8%; 159 people), 29-39 (31.6%; 95 people), and 40 and over (15.6%; 47 people). In terms of gender, women made up 67.8% (204 people), while men made up 32.2% (97 people).

4.1. Factor, Reliability, and Normality Analyses

According to the exploratory factor analysis performed on the three items designed to measure the frequency of chatting with artificial intelligence; the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sample adequacy coefficient, which is expected to be at least greater than 0.5 (Field, 2000), was determined as 0.67, and the Bartlett's sphericity test significance level was set at 0.000. Accordingly, a single factor explaining 66.9% of the total variance and with the lowest factor loading of 0.758 was identified. In addition, the overall mean of the variable is around 2.02 (about "rarely - a few times a year/few months"), and the Skewness of 0.64 and Kurtosis of -0.6 indicate that the data can be considered to conform to a normal distribution. Furthermore, the reliability level of the scale was determined as 0.75 and sufficient.

Table 1. Factor, Reliability, and Normality Analysis for AI Friendship

	Factor Loading
Lately, I've been talking to an AI tool (ChatGPT, etc.) as if I were chatting with a friend.	0.86
I use artificial intelligence for everyday social conversations.	0.83
I would rather chat with artificial intelligence than interact with people.	0.76
KMO=0.67, Bartlett sig.=0.000, Eigenvalue= 2.00, Explained Variance= % 66.9, Cronbach Alpha=0.75, Mean=2.02, Skewness= 0.64, Kurtosis=-0.6	
Answer options: 1. Never, 2. Rarely (a few times a year/few months), 3. Sometimes (a few times a month), 4. Frequently (a few times a week), 5. Always (every day or several times a day)	

According to the exploratory factor analysis performed on the four items designed to measure flow experience, one question with a factor loading of 0.265 was removed from the analysis, and the analysis was repeated. Accordingly, the KMO value was found to be 0.645 and the Bartlett test was statistically significant, identifying a single factor explaining 64.864% of the total variance. Furthermore, the reliability coefficient of 0.704 is sufficient, and the Skewness of 0.326 and Kurtosis of -0.362 allow for the assumption that the data is normally distributed.

Table 2. Factor, Reliability, and Normality Analysis of Flow Experience in AI Chat

	Factor Loadings
I don't pay attention to anything else while chatting with AI.	,858
I get completely absorbed when chatting with AI.	,830
I enjoy chatting with artificial intelligence.	,722
KMO=0.645, Bartlett sig.=0.000, Eigenvalue= 1.946, Explained Variance = % 64.864, Cronbach Alpha=0.704, Mean=2.2359, Skewness = 0.326, Kurtosis =-0.362	
Answer options: 1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Undecided, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly agree	

Finally, according to the exploratory factor analysis performed on the six-item AI companion social support variable, the KMO value was determined to be 0.889 and the Bartlett value was found to be statistically significant. Accordingly, a single factor explaining 80.566% of the total variance was identified. Furthermore, the reliability coefficient was determined to be 0.950, which is high. The Skewness value of 1.111 and Kurtosis of 0.386 also indicate that the data can be considered to conform to a normal distribution. It is also observed that the mean of the social support variable is around rarely.

Table 3. Factor, Reliability, and Normality Analyses for Social Support from AI Companions

	Factor Loadings
When I feel bad, my AI companion helps me feel better.	,938
When I'm sad, my AI friend comforts me.	,924
When I'm tense or under pressure, my AI friend comforts me.	,914
When I'm stressed, my AI friend reduces my worries.	,893
Despite all the negativity (my poor communication, bad qualities, etc.), my AI friend understands me.	,857
During difficult times, I feel that my AI friend cares about me.	,856
KMO=0.889, Bartlett sig.=0.000, Eigenvalue= 4.834, Explained Variance= % 80.566, Cronbach Alpha=0.950, Mean=1.9114, Skewness=1.111, Kurtosis=0.386	
Answer options: 1. Never, 2. Rarely (a few times a year/few months), 3. Sometimes (a few times a month), 4. Frequently (a few times a week), 5. Always (every day or several times a day)	

4.2. Hypothesis Testing

According to the regression analysis conducted on the extent to which the independent variables of the study, social support and flow experience, explain AI conversational behaviour, the model is significant. The Durbin-Watson value, expected to be between 1.5 and 2.5 to avoid autocorrelation (Karagöz, 2017), was found to be 2.042. Furthermore, the Tolerance value, expected to be greater than 0.1, and the VIF values, expected to be less than 10 (O'Brien, 2007), were found to be within the specified ranges to detect multicollinearity. In conclusion, the independent variables explain approximately 48% of the variability in the dependent variable ($R^2=0.482$). Accordingly, social support ($S.\beta=0.488$) and flow experience ($S.\beta=0.293$) significantly and positively influence AI companionship. Based on these findings, the research hypotheses are supported.

Table 4. Regression Analysis

	U. β .	S. β .	t	Sig.	% 95 C.I.		Multicollinearity	
					LL	UL	Tolerance	VIF
Flow experience in AI chat	,347	,293	5,842	,000	,230	,464	,691	1,446
Social support from AI companion	,432	,488	9,732	,000	,344	,519	,691	1,446
R= 0.695, R ² =0.482, Durbin-Watson= 2.042, F=138.849, sig.=0.000								

4.3. Examining Differences

When possible differences in research variables according to gender were examined with an independent samples t-test, no significant difference was found in the frequency of AI friendship/chat variable. On the other hand, it was determined that the social support variable from AI friends and the flow experience in chatting with AI were significantly higher in women.

Table 5. Differences According to Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	SS	Sig.
AI friendship/chat frequency	Male	97	1,8832	,89758	0,09
	Female	204	2,0784	,94591	
Flow experience in AI chat	Male	97	2,1031	,84760	0,043
	Female	204	2,2990	,75115	
Social support from AI companion	Male	97	1,5945	,82247	0,000
	Female	204	2,0621	1,11942	

Differences in research variables based on the most recent educational level are revealed using ANOVA tests. Intergroup differences were examined using the LSD test when group variances were homogeneous, and the Games-Howell test when they were not. Accordingly, there is no significant difference in the flow experience. On the other hand, differences were detected in the variables of AI friendship/chat frequency and social support from AI friends. According to the analysis results, the AI friendship/chat frequency variable shows that those with a “high school education or lower” level have significantly higher averages than those with a “bachelor's degree” and “master's degree or higher” level. In terms of the AI social support variable averages, those in the “high school education or lower” group have significantly higher averages than those in the “master's degree or higher” group.

Table 6. Differences According to Education Level

		N	Mean	SS	Sig.	Levene	Post hoc Tests
AI friendship/chat frequency	1.High school and below	94	2,2021	,96066	0,04 2	0.707, sig.=0.549	1-3; sig.=0.042 1-4; sig.=0.009
	2.Associate degree	71	2,0704	,93760			
	3.Bachelor's degree	68	1,9020	,90706			
	4. Master's degree and above	68	1,8137	,87981			
Flow experience in AI chat	1.High school and below	94	2,3617	,82763	0,20 5	1.809, sig.=0.146	-
	2.Associate degree	71	2,2582	,80118			
	3.Bachelor's degree	68	2,1373	,70590			
	4. Master's degree and above	68	2,1373	,78382			
Social support from AI companion	1.High school and below	94	2,0993	1,24586	0,03 8	10.452, sig.=0.000	1-4; sig.=0.049
	2.Associate degree	71	2,0258	1,13097			
	3.Bachelor's degree	68	1,7598	,85972			
	4. Master's degree and above	68	1,6838	,78181			

No significant differences were found when examining possible differences in research variables according to age. However, when examining differences according to occupation, significant differences were found in the variables of friendship/chat frequency and social support. Accordingly, it was observed that the average frequency of AI companionship/chat was significantly higher for private sector employees and students compared to public sector employees, and students had a higher average than those who were not working. In addition, it was determined that the average level of receiving social support from AI was higher for private sector employees and students compared to public sector employees.

Table 7. Differences According to Employment Status

		N	Mean	SS	Sig.	Levene	Post hoc tests
AI friendship/chat frequency	1. Private sector employee	55	2,1273	,96116	0,001	1.217, sig.=0.304	1-2; sig.=0.020 2-3; sig.=0.000 4-5; sig.=0.043
	2. Public sector employee	98	1,7687	,85676			
	3. Student	108	2,2593	,93655			
	4.Unemployed	31	1,8817	,91307			
Flow experience in AI chat	1. Private sector employee	55	2,2727	,73449	0,330	1.033, sig.=0.378	-
	2. Public sector employee	98	2,1361	,75655			
	3. Student	108	2,3364	,83597			
	4.Unemployed	31	2,2796	,79394			
Social support from AI companion	1. Private sector employee	55	2,0364	,94319	0,004	10.209, sig.=0.000	1-2; sig.=0.031 2-3; sig.=0.002
	2. Public sector employee	98	1,6190	,76582			
	3. Student	108	2,1343	1,21420			
	4.Unemployed	31	1,8495	1,19904			

4.4. Analysis of Distributions

The distributions of the research variables were analyzed by grouping them to better understand their levels. Accordingly, when the frequency values of the AI companionship or AI chat variable were examined, it was understood that 73.1% of the participants generally chatted with AI to some extent. Accordingly, it was determined that 23.3% of the participants chatted less than rarely (a few times a year/few months), and 27.5% chatted at a frequency of rarely (a few times a year/few months) or more but less than sometimes (a few times a month). The rate of those who chatted at a frequency of sometimes (a few times a month) or more was determined to be 22.3%.

Table 8. Examination of AI Companionship/Chat Behaviour (C) Groups

	Q	%
C=Never	81	26,9
Never < C < Rarely (a few times a year/few months)	70	23,3
Rarely (a few times a year/few months) ≤ C < Sometimes (a few times a month)	83	27,5
Sometimes (a few times a month) ≤ C < Always (every day or several times a day)	67	22,3
Total	301	100,0

When responses to the flow experience during the conversation with AI were grouped and analyzed, it was observed that 78.4% of respondents had an average score lower than undecided. The percentage of those at least at the undecided level and above was determined to be 21.6%. Overall, only 3.3% of respondents had an average score of "agree" or higher.

Table 9. Examination of AI Chat Flow Experience (F) Groups

	Q	%
F < I disagree	96	31,9
I disagree ≤ F < Undecided	140	46,5
Undecided ≤ F < I agree	55	18,3
I agree ≤ F ≤ I strongly agree	10	3,3
Total	301	100,0

When the averages of the AI companion social support variable for the participants were grouped, it was observed that the percentage of those who stated that they received no social support was 36.2%. Furthermore, the percentage of those who received support more than never but less than rarely (a few times a year/few months) was 22.9%. In addition, the percentage of those who received support rarely (a few times a year/few months) or more but less than sometimes (a few times a month) was 21.9%. Finally, the percentage of those who received social support sometimes (a few times a month) or more was determined to be 18.9%.

Table 10. Examination of Social Support (SS) Groups from AI Companions

	Q	%
SS=Never	109	36,2
Never < SS < Rarely (a few times a year/few months)	69	22,9
Rarely (a few times a year/few months) ≤ SS < Sometimes (a few times a month)	66	21,9
Sometimes (a few times a month) ≤ SS < Always (every day or several times a day)	57	18,9
Total	301	100

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The finding that social support received from an AI friend positively influences the frequency of AI companionship/chat is similar to research findings in the literature showing that AI is used to reduce loneliness (De Freitas et al., 2025; Syed, 2024; Al Mazroui & Alzyoudi, 2024), that those with limited social networks are more likely to use chatbots for friendship (Zhang et al., 2025), engage in socially supportive conversations (Herbener & Damholdt, 2025), that AI can be seen as always accessible support or therapy (Pataranutaporn et al., 2025), and that it can provide emotional support (Jämting, 2025; Sullivan et al., 2023). Furthermore, the research finding that the flow experience during conversations with an AI friend affects the frequency of AI friendship/conversation aligns with the findings of studies (Ding & Najaf, 2024; Wang et al., 2025; Kim et al., 2025; Arora et al., 2025) showing that the enjoyment variable plays a significant role in the intention to adopt or use AI tools.

In addition, the study determined that women experience a higher flow experience and receive social support in AI friendships. It was also found that those with a high school education or lower had higher levels of AI friendship or conversation compared to those with a bachelor's, master's/higher degree. Social support was also found to be higher in the high school and lower education group compared to the master's/higher education group. It is considered that the higher levels of AI friendship and social support among those with relatively lower education levels may be related to the limited social opportunities and high levels of loneliness associated with their educational status.

In addition, no difference was found in the flow experience based on employment status. On the other hand; private sector employees and students have significantly higher average AI companionship compared to public sector employees. Furthermore, students have higher AI companionships than non-employees. Additionally, the average level of social support is higher among students and private sector employees compared to public sector employees. The higher levels in these variables among private sector employees may be related to the challenging and limited living conditions of them compared to public sector employees, while students have relatively more time available for AI interaction and experience more negative situations such as stress and uncertainty.

This study determined that AI applications, which have gained popularity in recent years, are used not only for functional purposes but also for friendship, and that social support received from AI friends and the flow experience during conversations with AI are influential factors. In conclusion, it is understood that meeting the social support need by chatting with AI and experiencing flow experience while chatting with AI particularly influence the act of chatting with AI. The research provides insights into how or through

what mechanisms AI will affect people's social lives in the future. It is expected that the research findings will offer useful perspectives in terms of theoretical viewpoints, methods, and variables for future related research. From a marketing perspective, it is possible to examine the benefits of social support and the presence of a flowing experience in customer interactions or in AI applications used as part of a product, and their impact on the consumers.

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